

Citizen Science

What is it?

Public participation in research, when volunteers help scientists collect, analyze, or share data.

Importance

It accelerates discoveries through collaborative effort and promotes scientific literacy and open science.

Where to find?

Try Zooniverse, SciStarter, BOINC, or BürgerSchaffenWissen

New ideas?

Contact one of the Citizen Science Associations mentioned on the back!

Fact sheet

- Read more on the topic:
 - Finger, L., et al. The science of citizen science: a systematic literature review on educational and scientific outcomes. *Frontiers in Education*. Vol. 8. Frontiers Media SA, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2023.1226529>
 - Baytok, H. Participation in citizen science: motivational and contextual factors. Diss. Université Paris-Saclay, 2024. <https://theses.hal.science/tel-04661836>
 - Tokareva, V., et al. Citizen Science in Data-Intensive Physics: PUNCH4NFDI Perspective, 1.1, Zenodo, [doi:10.5281/zenodo.12743999](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12743999). DPG-Frühjahrstagung (DPG Spring Meeting) (DPG-24)Karlsruhe.
- Big Citizen Science Platforms:
 - **Zooniverse** – <https://www.zooniverse.org>
 - **SciStarter** – <https://scistarter.org>
 - **BOINC (Berkeley Open Infrastructure for Network Computing)** – <https://boinc.berkeley.edu>
 - **Bürger schaffen Wissen** – <https://www.buergerschaffenwissen.de>
 - **EU-Citizen.Science** – <https://eu-citizen.science>
 - **CitSci.org** – <https://citsci.org>
- Citizen Science associations in DACH and Europe:
 - **European Citizen Science Association (ECSA)** – <https://ecsa.citizen-science.net>
 - **Bürger schaffen Wissen (GEWISS)** – <https://www.buergerschaffenwissen.de>
 - **Österreich forscht (Austrian Citizen Science Platform)** – <https://www.citizen-science.at>
 - **Schweiz forscht (Swiss Citizen Science Network)** – <https://www.schweiz-forscht.ch>
 - **Deutsche Gesellschaft für Citizen Science (DGCS)** – <https://www.citizen-science.de>

This work is licensed under: CC BY 4.0
<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>